

CEMENT COMPOSITE STAY-IN-PLACE FORMWORK: A CONCEPT FOR FUTURE BUILDING SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The use of a recently developed inorganic phosphate cement with grain sizes less than 100 micrometer in combination with an adapted manufacturing process creates the possibility to obtain cement composites with a never been seen fiber volume ratio (V_f) of up to 25-30%, a factor 2 to 10 times higher than conventional cement composites. The forthcoming gain in tensile strength enables the material to be used in high performance building applications such as sandwich panels, structural claddings and concrete repair.

This paper presents a concept for a lightweight stay-in-place cement composite formwork taking advantage of this new promising material. Full scale tests analyzing the structural behavior indicate the opportunities of this innovative forming technique. Results also show an improved mechanical behavior of the composite (concrete-formwork) beam as the micro cracking phenomenon of concrete in tension is better controlled and crack propagation is delayed compared to a traditional steel reinforced concrete beam.

1 Introduction

Concrete is used more than any other man-made material in the world [1]. As of 2006, about 7.5 cubic kilometers or 18 trillion kilograms of concrete are being produced each year [2]. Concrete defined itself during the past century to be the primary material for constructions.

As buildings of the future tend to gain in complexity, also their cost will augment. One way to reduce their overall cost is to optimize the amount of material used in the structure. However, this approach overlooks the most important component in reinforced concrete structure cost: its formwork.

The largest part of this cost is defined by the cost of the labor to produce, place and eventually re-use the formwork system. These formwork costs transcend often more than 50% of the total cost of a concrete structural element and represent about 10% of the overall cost of the shell. Figure 1 illustrates the true cost of a reinforced concrete beam using traditional wood forming technologies and steel as reinforcement materials [3].

Fig 1: True cost of a structural element.

For many years, and even still today, these wood forms have been the general forming way. In the past decades however, wood forming has been challenged by a result of worldwide restrictions on harvesting. Numerous alternatives to wood have therefore been proposed including steel, PVC and polymer composite materials.

A focus was placed in the study of flexibility and ease of erecting of such formwork systems. Throughout the years many different systems were defined amongst which the conventional Stay-In-Place (SIP) forming system.

Early versions of SIP forming systems did however not satisfy the designer's expectations due to inflexibility of design and the fact that many materials lacked the necessary composition to offer long term cladding of the alkaline concrete structure. In addition, early SIP products had some barriers from design deficiencies that replaced traditional methodologies with an alternative set of construction challenges. With the recent development of composite materials, SIP systems are offering architects and engineers numerous advantages over competitive systems such as maximum flexibility, cost saving and efficient time control [4].

Recent advances in Textile Reinforced Cement Composites allow them to have considerably high fiber volume fractions. These so called high performance textile reinforced cement composites (HPTRCC) can, after the fulfillment of their primary purpose (defining the shape of the fresh concrete), also actively participate in the structural behavior while preserving their lightweight advantages.

The lightweight SIP can contribute for example to the load bearing capacity, improve the elements immune system against chemical or thermal attacks and even play a visual role as a finishing layer of the concrete element. Being a composite with an inorganic matrix, the material also shows resistance to elevated temperatures which is fundamental for building applications.

2 Lightweight SIP formwork for beams: design concept

The use of a HPTRCC in a formwork system can, due to its tensile capacity, (partially) replace steel reinforcement in concrete structures. A lightweight design moreover will create possibilities for easy placing. The freeform advantages of composite materials lead to an optimized material use of the load bearing element.

An easy to transport and easy to place lightweight formwork system will benefit the overall erection time and will decrease the carbon footprint of the construction phase, creating both economical and ecological advantages. A light and slender design however, imposes a radical change in forming concept.

To exploit the full potential of an easy to transport and easy to place forming system, temporary supporting structures in the hardening stage should be minimized. A free working span of 5 meters has therefore been set as a minimum span. However, not only over its length, but also in cross section the slender forming element has to withstand the fresh concrete pressures in order to result in a shape as defined by the designer. From these observations the hereafter discussed innovative SIP formwork concept is developed.

A stiff horizontal element will be used to transfer the gravity load of the fresh concrete to the supports rather than using conventional vertical struts for supporting the formwork (Figure 2). This approach creates an open workspace underneath the beam under construction and saves resources related to the use of temporary supporting structures. This hollow tubular element will be embedded in the final concrete element.

Fig 2: Supporting structure for formwork. External for traditional formwork, integrated for concept SIP

The tubular element not only has to bear forces generated in the casting stage, it will also in hardened stage take part in the load bearing function of the concrete beam. This element will be positioned in the tensile area of the load bearing member and will play part in the longitudinal reinforcement of the beam.

The element can be HPTRCC or polymer matrix composite material. It can vary in cross section where needed to provide longitudinal reinforcement to the concrete beam: in its bottom quarter the cross section can be enlarged. This quarter can contain stiff unidirectional reinforcement (carbon or steel) whereas chopped strand mats can be used in the remaining section (Figure 4).

The opening created by this encapsulated hollow element could, in addition to the load bearing

function, be used in various ways. For example, it can be seen as a shaft for the integration of techniques such as ventilation and electricity. Also, in the scope of durable housing, the opening can be used for structural repair and/or strengthening of the concrete element avoiding the use of future resources needed to replace the (damaged) element. Furthermore, a reduction in cross section in the tensile area of the concrete member immediately is translated in a decrease of material use which benefits the overall weight of the structure. This reduced use of material resources is directly linked to the concrete element's carbon footprint.

The U-shape placed around the tubular element will form the concrete's outer and visible cross section (figure 3). By means of a clip-on system the U-shape is anchored on its top-side. As displayed in figure 3 the flanges will due to the gravity forces of the fresh concrete, be pre-stressed in tension and aiding the formworks resistance versus bending invoked by the horizontal forces of the fresh concrete. The rounded edges at the bottom will limit stress concentrations whereas the curly ends at the top will hinder the buckling of the flanges in both fresh and hardened state. Furthermore will they be used to support the formwork on the clip-on system.

Fig 3: principal U-shape during casting

In hardened state the U-shape will contribute to the shear reinforcement of the beam (avoiding the need of steel stirrups). Defined by the direction of shear cracking in concrete beams chopped strand mat textiles were opted for as reinforcement.

Given the fact that this formwork is in direct contact to the composite-beams environment, it has to be able to withstand elevated temperatures in case of fire. Therefore a cement matrix is used. This choice moreover maintains the concrete appearance of the

beam, which is in contrast with the use of polymer based composites in building applications.

Fig 4: Cross-section composite member

The global SIP formwork concept here proposed (Figure 5) is based on the state of the art of cement composites. Research on both material and manufacturing level - hereafter explained - were exploited in order to break with traditional forming and concrete technologies.

Fig 5: Concept lightweight SIP

3 Advances in Textile Reinforced Concrete

Due to the degradation of glass fibers in an alkaline environment it is impossible to use standard E-glass fibers in combination with an ordinary Portland cement mortar [5]. Furthermore is the obtained fiber volume fraction in traditional fiber reinforced cements (FRC) limited to 2-5%, which actually limits the use of fiber reinforced cement composites in building applications to (quasi-)non load bearing elements or sub elements like infill wall panels and exterior cladding. A cement composite for structural use must meet the highest performance requirements, as defined in [6]:

- multiple cracking with crack width control: limitation of crack opening under tensile stress is obtained with a good bond between

fibers and matrix, and a large length to diameter ratio of the fibers;

- post-cracking stiffness, or strain hardening: this is essentially proportional to V_f and to the stiffness of the fibers, who ideally should be aligned with the applied stress;
- high tensile strength: in addition to high V_f , stiffness and alignment, the fibers should also be strong.

These requirements imply the use of a continuous fiber system (the fibers themselves may be continuous or discontinuous), usually termed as textile reinforcement, such as knitted or woven fabrics, or chopped strand mats. The common manufacturing processes for cementitious composites are not suited to meet these requirements, and production techniques of polymer matrix composites have to be adopted, capable of handling high volume fractions of fibers (in excess of 10%).

To circumvent these problems, the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) developed an Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC) that is acidic in fresh state, but pH neutral after hardening. Due to its fine particle size and the use of an adapted manufacturing process (see part 4) for the impregnation of fibrous textiles, a volume percent of 20-30% (a factor 3 to 10 times higher than conventional cement composites) can be obtained.

The constitutive behavior under compressive stress states of the resulting High Performance Textile Reinforced Cement Composite (HPTRCC) can be assumed to be linearly elastic until failure (± 60 MPa). Under tensile stresses on the contrary, the composite shows a complex and non-linear stress-strain evolution [7], which is represented in figure 6.

Using randomly orientated chopped strand mats as textile reinforcement, the composite possesses a tensile strength of up to 65 MPa. When unidirectional E-glass fibers are used, a tensile stress of even ± 200 MPa can be obtained, opening the possibility for the textile reinforced cement to take a load bearing function.

Extensive testing on repeated loading, freeze-thaw resistance and wetting and drying behavior have been performed on this HPTRCC. All tests indicated

a considerable improvement in durability compared to traditional TRC [8,9].

Fig 6: Tensile behavior HPTRCC IPC .

4 Advances in manufacturing

Due to the nature of cement as matrix for composites, being a mixture of a liquid and a powder, common manufacturing processes such as compression molding, pultrusion and resin transfer molding cannot be used to create HPTRCC. Its dense fiber structures will work as a filter and cause de-mixing of the powder and liquid component. Hand lay-up, with its known disadvantages of low volume (and thus high cost) production, is at present the only valid processing technique to obtain a higher V_f in cement matrix composites. Based on this principle the Vrije Universiteit van Brussel developed an impregnation technique suited for processing HPTRCC IPC on an industrial scale. Figure 7 shows the working principle of the impregnation technique, called self compacting impregnator (SCI).

Two cylinders are rotating in opposite sense around parallel horizontal axes, leaving only a limited opening between their surfaces. This creates, between their upper half surfaces, a receptacle filled with fresh matrix mixture, which is continuously consumed during the rotation of the cylinders. As such, two or more textile structures are continuously impregnated at the same time, with the cylinders controlling the speed of production through a

movable support which is in contact with one of the cylinders [10].

Fig 7: Working principle of SCI

The force by which the matrix is impregnated through the textile and the orientation of the fabrics is compared to hand lay-up, but not operator dependent. This results in an improved mechanical behavior.

5 Experiments and results

In order to study the mechanical behavior of a concrete member casted in a lightweight SIP, preliminary tests have been performed. Figure 8 presents the load-deflection curves of a steel-reinforced beam and a beam with the same longitudinal reinforcement, but with a U-shaped shear reinforcement SIP formwork of HPTRCC. The beams (0.2 x 0.3 x 2.3m) were loaded under four-point bending with third-point loading.

Due to the effect of the mechanical interaction between the HPTRCC laminates and the concrete, a delay of crack formation combined with a denser cracking pattern was noticed. Remarkably, the experimental cracking moment is more than twice as high for the HPTRCC reinforced beam as for the solely steel reinforced one. The resulting higher stiffness and thus lower deflection can be useful in cases where the serviceability limit state is governing. To achieve these results, a thickness of only 2 mm HPTRCC was needed [11,12].

Fig 8: Load vs. deflection curve HPTRCC reinforced beam

6 Conclusions

The ongoing study in both HPTRCC and its related manufacturing process performed at VUB leads to opportunities for the use of these composites in structural building applications. A formwork concept has been proposed based on the benefits of this material. The innovation breaks with all traditional forming rules and reinvents the way concrete can be used on site: lightweight elements can be transported and placed without the use of heavy equipment, while the labor intensive use of traditional steel reinforcement is minimized. The lightweight and easy to place aspect combined with the decrease in weight will benefit precious resources on both ecological and economical level.

Experimental work indicated the possibility of reinforcing a concrete beam with SIP HPTRCC formwork. The proposed concept however needs to be studied more deeply. This includes a better knowledge of the interaction between concrete and formwork.

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